

Studies on some Thiadiazolotriazines as Potential Fungicides

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The fungicidal potency of pyrimidine triazine and thiadiazole derivatives is well documented. In particular, a large number of pyrimidine derivatives have found practical application as agricultural and industrial fungicides¹. Amongst triazine derivatives, a compound of special significance is 2-thiocyanatotriazine² which is not only a protective fungicide for seeds, plants, and fruits but also checks the growth of soil fungi.

A thiadiazolotriazine (1) may be viewed as an amalgamation of pyrimidine and thiadiazole moieties. As such it may be expected to display enhanced fungicidal properties. With a view to explore this possibility, the synthesis and bioassay of the title compounds were undertaken.

Experimental

M.ps. were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. The purity of compounds were checked by tlc.

2-Amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles: These were synthesised by cyclodehydration of aroyl thiosemicarbazide by following the reported method³.

2-Arylideneamino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles: These Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles with the appropriate araldehyde in usual way. Their ir spectra and elemental analysis (N and S) were compatible with their structures.

2,6,7-Triaryl-1,3,4-thiadiazolo[2,3-b]-s-triazine-5-thiones (1a-h): To a solution of 2-arylideneamino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (0.01 mol) in xylene was added appropriate arylisothiocyanate (0.01 mol) taken in same solvent. The mixture was refluxed

3-4 h. The solvent was then removed, the residue was washed successively with ether and water, and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol (Table 1): ν_{\max} 1 170-1 100 (C=S) and 1 645-1 610 cm^{-1} (C=N stretch of the ring).

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS (1a-h)*

Compd. no.	Ar ₁	Ar ₂	M.p. °C
1a	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Ar= <i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	260
		<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	
b	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Ar= <i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -	250
		<i>p</i> -CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	
c	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	265
		<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	
d	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ar= <i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	244
		<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	
e	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	Ar=2,4-diClC ₆ H ₃	238
		<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	
f	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	247
		<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	
g	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	240
		<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	
h	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	255
		<i>p</i> -OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₄	

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and S analyses.

The antifungal activity of the title compounds (1a-h) were evaluated against *P. oryzae* and *F. oxysporum* by modified paper disc technique⁴ in three different concentrations (1000, 100 and 10 mg dm⁻³). Dithane M-45, a commercial fungicide, was used as control. Compounds 1b-d were comparable with Dithane (100% inhibition) and rest of the compounds were less active against both the microorganisms.

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NOTES

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